

Enhancing Radiologist Reading Performance by Ordering Screening Mammograms Based on Characteristics that Promote Visual Adaptation

Radiologist Screening Performance when Reading Mammograms in Different Orders

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Abbreviations:

AUC = area under the ROC curve, BI-RADS = Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System, ROC = receiver operating characteristic, SSL = self-supervised learning, TTF = time to first fixation, VBD = volumetric breast density

Summary:

Reading screening mammography examinations ordered from low to high volumetric breast density improved radiologists' screening performance while reducing reading and fixation times compared with reading randomly ordered screening examinations.

Key results:

- In a retrospective multireader multicase study of an enriched dataset of mammograms from 150 women, the reader-averaged area under the receiver operating characteristic curve was greater when radiologists interpreted images ordered by increasing volumetric breast density (VBD) versus randomly (0.93 vs 0.92; $P = .009$).
- Reading time (reduced by 3.6 seconds), fixation counts (reduced by five fixations), and fixation duration in the malignant lesion regions (reduced by 0.9 second) were lower when radiologists interpreted examinations ordered by increasing VBD versus randomly ($P < .001$).

Abstract

Background:

Mammographic background characteristics may stimulate human visual adaptation, allowing radiologists to detect abnormalities more effectively. However, it is unclear whether density, or another image characteristic, drives visual adaptation.

Purpose:

To investigate whether screening performance improves when screening mammography examinations are ordered for batch reading according to mammographic characteristics that may promote visual adaptation.

Materials and Methods:

This retrospective multireader multicase study was performed with mammograms obtained between September 2016 and May 2019. The screening examinations, each consisting of four mammograms, were interpreted by 13 radiologists in three distinct orders: randomly, by increasing volumetric breast density (VBD), and based on a self-supervised learning (SSL) encoding (examinations automatically grouped as 'looking similar'). An eye tracker recorded radiologists' eye movements during interpretation. The area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC), sensitivity, and specificity of random-ordered readings were compared with those of VBD- and SSL-ordered readings using mixed-model analysis of variance. Reading time, fixation metrics, and perceived density were compared using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests.

Results:

Mammography examinations (75 with breast cancer, 75 without breast cancer) from 150 women (median age, 55 years [IQR, 50–63]) were read. The examinations ordered by increasing VBD versus randomly had an increased AUC (0.93 [95% CI: 0.91, 0.96] vs 0.92 [95% CI: 0.89, 0.95], $P = .009$), without evidence of a difference in specificity (89% [871 of 975] vs 86% [837 of 975], $P = .04$) and sensitivity (both 81% [794 of 975 vs 788 of 975], $P = .78$), and a reduced reading time (24.3 vs 27.9 seconds, $P < .001$), fixation count (47 vs 52, $P < .001$), and fixation time in malignant regions (3.7 vs 4.6 seconds, $P < .001$). For SSL-ordered readings, there was no evidence of differences in AUC (0.92, [95% CI: 0.89, 0.95], $P = .70$), specificity (84% [820 of 975], $P = .37$), sensitivity (80% [784 of 975], $P = .79$), fixation count (54, $P = .05$), or fixation time in malignant regions (4.6 seconds, $P > .99$) compared to random-ordered readings. Reading times were significantly higher for SSL-ordered readings compared to random-ordered readings (28.4 seconds, $P = .02$).

Conclusion:

Screening mammography examinations ordered from low to high VBD improved screening performance while reducing reading and fixation times.

Introduction

Breast cancer screening has significantly improved the early detection of malignancies, thereby reducing breast cancer mortality (1–3). However, given the challenging task of identifying cancers in complex mammographic backgrounds, the high volume of screening examinations, and the low prevalence of breast cancers at screening, there is a need to find strategies to increase the efficiency and accuracy of screening interpretation (4–6). Retrospective studies revealed that 20%-50% of the interval and screen-detected cancers were visible in prior screening mammograms (7–12), suggesting that mammography alone could have been sufficient for detection of these cancers. These findings emphasize the potential to improve the interpretation of mammograms, hopefully resulting in earlier detection and improved prognosis.

Visual judgments of screening radiologists are affected by processes of human perception, including cognitive, perceptual, and decision-making factors, many of which have been studied in the context of mammography (13–18). One such perceptual process is visual adaptation, which refers to changes in the sensitivity and operating characteristics of the visual system in response to the current stimuli the observer is viewing (19–21). Visual adaptation can have a large influence on the appearance of images, known as visual aftereffects (22), and can also influence visual performance by altering sensitivity or the detectability of stimuli. For example, adaptation may serve to discount the expected properties of a visual environment, thereby enhancing the visual salience of unexpected information (23,24).

Few studies have considered adaptation in the context of radiologic assessments. However, Kompaniez-Dunigan et al. reported that exposure to mammogram patches altered how dense, fatty (14), or blurry (13) the images appeared. They also found that search times for simulated targets in fatty or dense mammogram patches were faster when the nonradiologist observers were adapted to images of the background type within which they were searching (15). More recently, Parthasarathy et al. (25) reported similar adaptation aftereffects in digital breast tomosynthesis images. Although these results suggest that adaptation could significantly impact perception and performance during radiologic readings, a limitation was that these studies were conducted with nonradiologists under controlled conditions. Thus, the question remains whether similar adaptation effects manifest in screening radiologists in an actual screening reading environment.

Leveraging visual adaptation for batch reading screening mammograms requires the interpreting radiologist to be adapted to the characteristics of the mammogram they are reading. To do this, the mammograms for interpretation need to be ordered so that images with characteristics that promote similar visual adaptation are grouped together. It is not clear, however, whether mammographic density, or another more complex image characteristic, is the main driver of visual adaptation for the interpreting radiologist. To the best of our knowledge, there have been no previous attempts to order screening mammograms for individual batch reading based on image properties.

Therefore, the aim of this study was to determine whether the screening performance of radiologists during batch reading of screening mammograms can be improved when the screening examinations are ordered according to characteristics that may promote visual adaptation.

Materials and Methods

The need for ethical approval for this retrospective multireader multicase study was waived by the Research Ethics Committee of Radboud University Medical Center (registration number 2021-13186).

Study Sample

The screening examinations consisted of anonymized two-view (craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique) bilateral mammograms from the Dutch National Breast Cancer Screening Program. The mammograms were acquired between September 2016 and May 2019 using digital mammography systems (Lorad Selenia and Selenia Dimensions; Hologic) in accordance with Dutch guidelines, which involves the use of the automatic exposure control to set the technique for each image acquisition.

Screening examinations were randomly selected to achieve the target area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (AUC) as described in the statistical analyses section.

Mammograms of women with breast implants and examinations with missing images or ground truth data were excluded. Ground truth data included biopsy-proven cancers and noncancers with at least two years of follow-up. Findings of all noncancer examinations were classified as either true-negative or false-positive, depending on whether the women were recalled. Data to distinguish between normal (healthy breast tissue) and benign (nonmalignant lesions) findings were not available, and information about histopathologic tumor types, tumor sizes, and lesion types was retrieved through linkage with the national cancer registry.

Mammogram Ordering

Three approaches for ordering mammography examinations for reading were tested.

In the first approach, screening examinations were ordered by increasing volumetric breast density (VBD) percentage (Volpara®Density™, version 1.5.4.0; Volpara Health Technologies), based on the average VBD of the four mammograms within each examination. Increasing VBD, as opposed to decreasing, was chosen to allow radiologists to start their sessions with low-density mammograms that represent an easy reading task, with a slow transition toward more difficult-to-interpret, higher-density mammograms.

As stated earlier, another more complex image characteristic might drive visual adaptation for radiologists. Therefore, the second approach was based on a deep learning network that was trained with self-supervised learning (SSL). Such a network is trained to summarize the information contained in an image by identifying several features. Although the features are not predefined by human input, the deep learning model was informed that features of different views (ie, craniocaudal vs mediolateral oblique), from rotated mammograms, and from mammograms of both breasts of the same woman should be similar, while features from mammograms of different women should be different. With this method, mammograms that look similar should also have similar features. For the SSL order, any screening examination could serve as the initial examination. In this study, examinations were selected based on the average feature values derived from all four mammograms within each examination. The examination with the most extreme features identified was selected first, followed by the next examination with features most similar to those of the just-selected examination. In that way, two consecutive screening examinations, each with its four mammograms, have minimal differences between their features. A detailed explanation of this encoding method can be found in Appendix S1.

In the third approach, the order of screening examinations was randomly generated and was used as a reference for current screening practice.

Observer Study

A fully crossed multireader multicase study was performed with three reading sessions, each separated by at least 2 weeks. Each session included one of three different orders of mammograms: VBD, SSL, or random order.

Thirteen screening-certified breast radiologists (including K.M.D., J.K.v.R., A.F.v.R., J.B.H., D.B.N.) from different reading units in the Netherlands participated. The 13 involved breast cancer screening radiologists had 4-32 years of experience with screening mammography (median, 12 years). The

radiologists, on average, spend 1.4 days per week on screening, and the median volume of screening examinations read per year was 11,000 (range, 10,000–22,000). All radiologists performed reading in all three sessions, with the order of the first, second, and third sessions randomized for each radiologist.

The eye movements of the radiologists were recorded with a remote eye tracker (Tobii Pro Spark; Tobii). Radiologists were pretrained with a set of 10-20 screening examinations to gain familiarity with the workstation. Radiologists did not have access to previous screening mammograms or any other personal information about the women and were informed about the study aim but were blinded to the specific orders being tested. Radiologists were able to zoom and switch between the mediolateral oblique and craniocaudal views, but they were not allowed to pan or adjust the window and level settings.

The 150 screening examinations were split into three reading batches of 50 examinations each and were read in the same day. For each screening examination, radiologists provided the following: (a) a case-based probability of a malignancy score ranging from 0 to 100 (100 indicating the highest suspicion of malignancy), (b) a Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System (BI-RADS), fifth edition, density category ranging from fatty (BI-RADS category a) to dense (BI-RADS category d) (26), and (c) a recall decision (yes or no). If radiologists decided to recall, they were instructed to mark the location for which they recalled the woman. Figure S1 shows the reader study interface. Reading times were recorded from the moment the screening examination first appeared until the radiologist moved to the next examination.

For all three ordering conditions, radiologists started reading the first screening examination without prior visual adaptation. To maintain visual adaptation after recalibration or a break, a readaptation movie was presented. This movie showed the five previous screening examinations from the preceding batch that day, each was displayed for 3 seconds in an order specific to the ordering condition of that day. More detailed information about the observer study can be found in Appendix S2.

Eye Tracker Data

Raw eye tracker data were classified into eye fixations, which are brief pauses during which the eyes cease movement and focus on specific points in the visual field. The classification of eye fixations included different data processing steps inspired by the Tobii I-VT Filter (27,28), as detailed in Appendix S3.

The total number of fixations per screening examination, combining fixations from both the craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique views (eg, yellow dots in Fig 1), was tracked. Additionally, the

time spent fixating within a 20-mm radius around the lesion center (defined as the lesion region, red circle in Fig 1) was measured. Finally, the time to first fixation (TTFF) in that lesion region was recorded, representing the time interval for a radiologist to notice the lesion from the moment the examination first appeared.

Statistical Analyses

To achieve a study power of 0.8 for the detection of a difference of at least 0.05 in the AUC, a minimum of 124 examinations were required for interpreting by the 13 readers (29). Therefore, for this study, a total of 150 screening examinations were randomly selected, including 75 with breast cancer and 75 with no cancer.

AUC analysis

As the primary outcome measure, the AUC for the random-ordered reading was compared with the AUC for the VBD- and SSL-ordered readings. For the multireader multicase analysis of variance, the ROC curves were plotted and their AUCs and 95% CIs were calculated using the radiologists' probability of malignancy scores (ranging from 0 to 100) and iMRMC software package (version 4.0.3; Division of Imaging, Diagnostics, and Software Reliability, Office of Science and Engineering Laboratories, Center for Devices and Radiological Health, U.S. Food and Drug Administration). Additional details about this analysis can be found in Appendix S4. *P* values were based on a *t* test, assuming that the test statistic followed a Student *t* distribution (30).

Specificity and sensitivity

As secondary outcome measures, reader-averaged specificity and sensitivity for the random-ordered readings were compared with those of the VBD- and SSL-ordered readings using the radiologists' recall decisions. This analysis was performed following the same statistics as described for the AUC analysis.

Reading times

The median reading times per examination across all 13 radiologists, which are less susceptible to being influenced by extreme values, were compared for the random-ordered readings against the VBD- and SSL-ordered readings. For this comparison, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used, accounting for the dependency of the paired examinations. Additional analyses on reading time were reported separately for Volpara Density Grades (categories a, b, c, and d), which correlate with visual BI-RADS 5th edition density categories (26).

Fixations

Eye tracking data were also compared using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, again taking paired screening examinations into account. For the examination-based comparisons, median values were calculated for the number of fixations, fixation duration on malignant lesion regions, and TTFF at those regions, using data from all 13 radiologists for each examination. When the eye tracker did not register fixations in the lesion region for a specific reader in a specific examination, TTFF outcomes for that reader and examination were excluded for all three orders to ensure that the median TTFF calculation for each reading order was based on data from the same readers.

Additional analyses on reading time and fixation outcomes were reported separately for cancer and noncancer examinations. These included examinations with unanimous radiologist agreement on the correct recall decision for all three orders (consensus) and those with disagreement (nonconsensus). The consensus examinations were assumed to be relatively easy and/or obvious. The nonconsensus examinations were assumed to be more difficult.

Density categories

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare the perceived BI-RADS density categories (categories, a, b, c, and d) (26) of the radiologists across the three different reading orders. Each radiologist-examination pair was analyzed by comparing the density categories of the different reading orders (150 examinations x 13 radiologists = 1950 radiologist-examination pairs per reading order).

Statistical significance for each end point was defined as a $P < .025$, which included the Bonferroni correction for the comparison of the random order against the VBD and SSL orders.

Results

Study Sample Characteristics

The study sample comprised screening examinations of 150 women (median age, 55 years [IQR 50–63]) (Table 1). The SSL order resulted in more occurrences of consecutive cancer and noncancer examinations than did the random and VBD orders (random: 2.3 ± 1.6 , VBD: 2.1 ± 1.5 , SSL: 6.0 ± 6.3) (Fig S2).

Performance Analysis

Compared with reading mammography examinations in random order, radiologists improved their screening performance when reading examinations by increasing VBD, with the reader-averaged AUC increasing from 0.92 (95% CI: 0.89, 0.95) to 0.93 (95% CI: 0.91, 0.96) ($P = .009$) (Fig 2). This

increased AUC was consistent for 12 of the 13 radiologists (Table S1). There was no evidence of a difference in the reader-averaged AUC between the random- and SSL-ordered readings (both 0.92 [95% CI: 0.89, 0.95]; $P = .70$). An ROC curve plot with 95% CIs is presented in Figure S3.

Specificity and Sensitivity

On average, with the Bonferroni correction, there was no evidence of a difference in reader-averaged specificity when comparing the random order with the increasing VBD and SSL order (random vs VBD: 837 of 975 [86%] vs 871 of 975 [89%], $P = .04$; random vs SSL: 837 of 975 [86%] vs 820 of 975, [84%], $P = .37$) (Fig 2, Table S2). Also, for radiologist-averaged sensitivities there was no evidence of a difference between the random-ordered readings and the VBD- and SSL-ordered readings (random vs VBD: 788 of 975 vs 794 of 975 [both 81%], $P = .78$; random vs SSL: 788 of 975 [81%] vs 784 of 975 [80%], $P = .79$). This finding was consistent across histopathologic tumor types, tumor sizes, and lesion types (Table S3).

Reading Times

The median reading time per screening examination was shorter when radiologists read examinations from low to high VBD than when they read examinations in random order (24.3 seconds vs 27.9 seconds, $P < .001$) (Fig 3). This effect was especially pronounced in Volpara Density Grades b, c, and d (Fig S4). Only for the obvious cancer examinations, where all radiologists agreed to recall the woman in all three reading orders, there was no evidence of a difference between the reading times of the VBD- and random-ordered readings ($P = .16$) (Fig S5). The median reading times were longer for the SSL-ordered readings than for the random-ordered readings (28.4 seconds vs 27.9 seconds, $P = .02$). Individual reading times are shown in Table S4.

Fixations

The median number of fixations and the time fixated on the malignant lesion regions were lower for the VBD-ordered reading than for the random-ordered reading (random vs VBD: 52 fixations vs 47 fixations, $P < .001$; 4.6 seconds vs 3.7 seconds in the lesion region, $P < .001$) (Fig 4, Table S4). There was no evidence of a difference between the random- and SSL-ordered readings for median number of fixations and fixation time within the lesion region (random vs SSL: 52 fixations vs 54 fixations, $P = .05$; both 4.6 seconds in the lesion region, $P > .99$). Figures S6 and S7 contain information about fixation outcomes categorized into consensus and nonconsensus examinations.

TTFF at the lesion region was faster for the true-positive examinations with consensus among all radiologists than for the nonconsensus examinations (Fig S8). However, there was no evidence of a

difference in median TTFF for the reading orders (random vs VBD: 1.1 seconds vs 1.0 second, $P = .20$; random vs SSL: 1.1 seconds vs 1.0 second, $P = .34$) (Fig 4, Table S4).

Density Category Assessments

Figure 5 shows how adaptation affected the mammographic density perceived by radiologists. The perceived density categories were different for the VBD- and random-ordered readings ($P < .001$) (Fig S9). Within the VBD order, radiologists classified more examinations as BI-RADS c and d and fewer as BI-RADS a and b. Differences in perceived density categories were also observed between the random- and SSL-ordered readings ($P = .02$), with both increasing and decreasing radiologist-perceived density.

Discussion

The results of our study show that reading screening mammography examinations ordered from low to high volumetric breast density (VBD), compared with reading in a random order, consistently improved radiologists' screening performance, as measured with the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) (0.93 vs 0.92, $P = .009$), while reducing reading time (24.3 seconds vs 27.9 seconds, $P < .001$) and lesion-fixation time (3.7 seconds vs 4.6 seconds, $P < .001$). By integrating quantitative density metrics into the screening workflow and implementing automated sorting algorithms in the screening worklist, organizing batch readings of screening examinations from low to high VBD would be feasible to implement and may serve as a valuable strategy to optimize breast cancer screening.

The improved screening performance and reduced reading time (especially in denser mammograms) when batch reading of examinations by increasing VBD aligns with the adaptation hypothesis (13,15,31). This hypothesis suggests that radiologists gradually adjust to the characteristic structure of mammograms, focusing on more unexpected properties and thereby improving performance and reducing reading time. Consistent with the reduced reading time, the number of fixations per screening examination and the fixation duration in the lesion region were also lower. This finding may indicate a more confident decision of the radiologist, causing them to have fewer fixations in the density-ordered reading. Alternatively, adaptation could indirectly affect fixations by increasing the effective salience of the targets. McDermott et al (23) also found changes in the number and duration of fixations following adaptation to different color distributions in a color search task, where observers located a color singleton on a dense background of distractors, but argued that this reflected changes in the relative stimulus contrast rather than in the way the images were sampled.

There was no evidence of a difference in diagnostic performance or fixation outcomes between the SSL-ordered reading and the random-ordered reading. However, the reading time was longer for SSL-ordered readings than for random-ordered readings. Interestingly, SSL-ordered reading resulted in numerous consecutive cancers and noncancers, for example, starting with 22 cancer examinations. This ordering may have influenced the radiologists by increasing their uncertainty and potentially affecting their decision making, which resulted in longer reading times. Despite this potential psychological effect, radiologists demonstrated comparable performance with SSL-ordered and random-ordered reading. The clustering effect of cancers will be less pronounced in a dataset with a cancer prevalence typical of screening. Hence, it is possible that SSL ordering will result in better outcomes in a screening setting where this clustering effect is less prevalent.

There was no evidence of differences in TTF in the lesion region across different reading orders, indicating that radiologists did not detect malignant lesions faster in any particular order. The enhanced performance with specific ordering may relate more to improved lesion characterization rather than faster detection. Visual adaptation may play a role in differentiating between normal versus unexpected characteristics in images (19–21). However, lesion characterization involves more complex cognitive processes, such as pattern recognition, knowledge of lesion characteristics, and clinical experience, as well as metacognition or confidence in judgments, which may be influenced by adaptation (32,33). Further research is needed to fully understand the influence of visual adaptation on radiologic assessments.

Radiologists batch reading the screening examinations by increasing VBD perceived the mammograms to be denser than when reading the mammograms in the SSL or random order. A previous study by Kompaniez-Dunigan et al (14) revealed that prior exposure to fatty mammogram patches caused an intermediate texture to appear denser and vice versa. This finding may explain why gradually increasing VBD caused the mammograms to look denser in the VBD-ordered reading.

It would be interesting to also investigate what happens if the density order is reversed—ordering by decreasing VBD, and thus starting with the highest-density mammograms, which are likely more difficult to interpret. Due to limitations in the number of ordering conditions that the readers could be asked to perform, we were not able to investigate this in our study. Radiologist preferences regarding the reading order and considerations about fatigue may ultimately also influence the most effective reading order.

Our study had limitations. First, the study was performed in an experimental setting with a cancer-enriched case set and no prior screening mammograms were available. High cancer prevalence can lead to higher sensitivity and lower specificity among radiologists, as found in prior research (5,34).

In addition, radiologists were aware of the enriched nature of the case set, which may have introduced a 'laboratory effect' (5,35). However, any such effect would have similarly affected all three reading conditions, thereby minimizing its impact on the ordering comparison. Future research should investigate ordering strategies in a real screening population, preferably through a prospective study. Second, our study was performed with screening radiologists from the Netherlands; however, screening practices around the world vary. Therefore, our results may not be generalizable to all other screening programs. Third, gaze point measurements are subject to error, potentially leading to variability in the accuracy of fixation outcomes. We tried to minimize those effects by applying different processing steps based on the principles of the Tobii I-VT Filter (27,28). Finally, for some examinations, we relied on visual inspection by screening radiologists for the lesion locations, as biopsy-proven locations were unavailable. The radiologists who provided these locations were not involved as readers in our study. While the absence of biopsy-proven locations may have affected lesion region fixation analyses, most reader localizations in this study aligned with our ground truth, minimizing the potential impact.

In conclusion, the findings of our study indicate that ordering mammography examinations from low to high volumetric breast density (VBD) improved screening performance while reducing reading and fixation times. Although larger studies are needed to validate these findings, our results suggest that ordering screening mammograms for reading by increasing VBD may be feasible. The integration of automated density algorithms could facilitate the organization of the screening program worklist. Assessing this ordered list may improve radiologists' ability to detect and characterize suspicious findings, potentially leading to better outcomes for screened women and increased efficiency. However, future research should assess what other order criteria may further optimize radiologists' screening performance (eg, reading by decreasing VBD or ordering by increasing probability of malignancy scores via artificial intelligence). If proven successful, future studies should also assess the effectiveness of these ordering strategies prospectively in actual screening settings.

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Tables

Table 1: Sample characteristics

Characteristic	Value
No. of women	150
Median age (y) [*]	55 (49–72, 50–63)
Median breast volume (cm ³) [†]	785.8 (511.4–1168.9)
Median compressed breast thickness (mm) [†]	58.5 (48.3–67.9)
Median percentage VBD [†]	7.6 (5.0–11.8)
Screening outcome [‡]	
True-positive	64 (43)
False-negative	11 (7)
True-negative	69 (47)
False-positive	4 (3)
Outcome	
Not malignant [§]	75 (50)
Malignant	75 (50)
Malignant lesion type ^{, #}	
Mass	43 (56)
Calcifications	22 (29)
Mass + calcifications	6 (8)
Architectural distortion	1 (1)
Architectural distortion + calcifications	2 (3)
Asymmetric density	3 (4)
Malignant histopathologic type ^{, **}	
Invasive NST	48 (62)
DCIS	17 (22)
ILC	7 (9)
Mixed NST/ILC	5 (6)
Other invasive	1 (1)
Median size of malignant lesions (mm) ^{†, ††}	16.0 (10.3–21.0)

Note. – Unless otherwise indicated, data in parentheses are percentages. DCIS = ductal carcinoma in situ, ILC = invasive lobular carcinoma, NST = no special type, VBD = volumetric breast density from VolparaDensity, version 1.5.4.0; Volpara Health Technologies.

* The first set of numbers in parentheses is the age range, and the second set is the IQR.

† Data in parentheses are the IQR.

‡ Screening outcome not available for two examinations.

§ Data to distinguish between normal and benign findings were not available.

|| Some screening examinations included multiple lesions, which resulted in more lesions than examinations.

Lesion type was not available for two malignant lesions.

** The type of histopathologic finding was not available for one malignant lesion.

†† Tumor diameter was not available for 21 malignant lesions, but the reason for this is unknown.

Figures

Figure 1: Mammograms in a 54-year-old woman with an invasive ductal carcinoma in the lateral upper quadrant of the left breast. The yellow dots represent eye fixations, and the red circle represents the lesion region. LCC = left craniocaudal, LMLO = left mediolateral oblique, RCC = right craniocaudal, RMLO = right mediolateral oblique.

Figure 2: Reader-averaged receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves for the radiologists reading screening mammography examinations that were ordered by increasing volumetric breast density (blue), randomly (red), and by self-supervised learning (SSL) (green). The dots indicate radiologists' operating points based on their recall decisions. AUC = area under the ROC curve, FPR = false-positive rate, TPR = true-positive rate.

Figure 3: Violin plot shows median reading times of the radiologists reading screening mammography examinations that were ordered randomly (red), by increasing volumetric breast density (blue), and by self-supervised learning (SSL) (green). The random reading order was compared against the density and SSL order, and the asterisks indicate statistical significance: *** $P < .0005$, * $P < .025$.

Figure 4: Violin plots show fixation outcomes for the radiologists reading screening mammography examinations that were ordered randomly (red), by increasing volumetric breast density (blue), and by self-supervised learning (SSL) (green). (A) The total number of fixations for the screening examinations (including fixations in both craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique views). (B) Fixation time in the 20-mm lesion region for the 75 screening examinations with malignant lesions. (C) Time to first fixation (TTFF) on the 20-mm radius lesion region in the 75 screening examinations with malignant lesions. The random reading order was compared against the density and SSL order, and the asterisks indicate statistical significance: *** $P < .0005$

Figure 5: Radiologists' perceived Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System categories. Outcomes from all radiologists and examinations were aggregated. The vertical dashed lines represent Volpara Density Grade percentage volumetric breast density (VBD) thresholds, which correlate with visual Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System, fifth edition, density categories (a < 3.5%, 3.5% ≤ b < 7.5%, 7.5% ≤ c < 15.5%, d ≥ 15.5%). SSL = self-supervised learning.

Appendix S1 - Self-supervised Learning Encoding

The self-supervised learning order (SSL) aims to group similar looking mammography examinations to minimize the change from one examination to the next. The definition of “looking similar” is not based on hand-crafted features, but features learned by a network that was trained with an SSL framework. For this, a Resnet-50 was trained with a SimCLR framework to create a 2048-feature encoding of a mammogram cropping (36). SimCLR is a contrastive SSL framework for visual representations. In contrastive learning, the distance between encodings of positive pairs of images is minimized while the distance between encodings of negative pairs is maximized. Positive pairs are usually defined by different transforms of the same image, for example a rotation or crop.

Transforms are chosen in such a way that an image after that transform should still receive the same encoding. For mammogram ordering, in this study the following transforms were selected: selection of a random crop of 35 x 35 mm out of any of the views, random flip and/or rotation, random color jitter, and random gaussian blur. Negative pairs were chosen as mammograms of different women. Using these definitions for positive and negative pairs will ensure that encodings of different views in the same examination will receive a similar encoding, while views from examinations of different women will receive a different encoding. The Resnet-50 was trained with a dataset of 43,443 Dutch screening examinations (both normal and cancer cases) of unique women consisting of four views each.

The SSL order of the 150 screening examinations in this study was defined in several steps. First, each mammographic view was segmented with a U-Net (37) to remove the background and pectoral muscle and the largest possible rectangle was fitted inside the breast. The resulting rectangles were used as input to the model, to avoid any influence from the shape and background. The output feature vectors were averaged over each rectangle of each of the four views to result in one feature vector for each screening examination. The examination with the maximum feature norm was selected as the starting examination. The next examination was the examination that minimized the Euclidean distance of the encodings with the previous just-selected one. This process was repeated until all examinations were selected in order.

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Appendix S2 - Observer Study Details

The reader study was performed in a controlled setting with ambient room lighting of approximately 45 lux. A twelve-megapixel monitor certified for breast imaging (Coronis Uniti, MDMC-12133 Barco) and calibrated to the DICOM grayscale standard display function was used.

The Tobii eye tracker, which was used during the study, was placed below the viewing monitor, and the radiologists' eye movements were recorded with a sampling frequency of 60 Hz without requiring the radiologists to wear any equipment or restricting their head movement. Before each session, a 9-point calibration process was performed to ensure accurate tracking of eye movements. A fixation cross was used before each examination to ensure eye tracker calibration. If needed, radiologists repeated the 9-point calibration step before proceeding to the next examination.

Reading times were also recorded. Any time spent recalibrating, taking breaks, or watching the readaptation movie was excluded from the recorded reading times. To prevent outliers in reading time due to interruptions, precautions were taken. Prior to the start of the study, the readers were instructed to use the restroom if necessary and to stow away their phones to minimize interruptions. Additionally, one of the authors remained present in the same room as the readers to ensure an uninterrupted study. Consequently, extreme reading times were not excluded, as it was believed that these deviations were justifiable and not attributable to interruptions.

Appendix S3 - Eye tracking data

Raw eye tracking data were classified into eye fixations using different data processing steps and default values inspired by the Tobii I-VT Filter (27,28). First, missing eye tracking data shorter than 75 msec, the default value chosen by Tobii, was linearly interpolated. Second, the average position of where the left and the right eye were looking, was calculated. If only one eye was detected by the eye tracker, the data from that eye was used. Next, noise was reduced by taking the moving median of three consecutive data points, the default value used by Tobii (28). Lastly, fixations were defined as consecutive gaze points with a velocity below 359 mm per second on the screen, considering the Tobii default velocity threshold of 30°/second (28,38) and assuming a distance of 67 cm between the reader and the screen. To prevent long fixations being split up by measurement errors, neighboring fixations that were within 75 msec and 6 mm of each other (27,28,39) and fell on the same image were merged. Fixations shorter than 60 msec were discarded as very short fixations are not meaningful when studying radiologist behavior where the eye and brain require some time to register and process visual information (27,28).

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Appendix S4 – Statistical Analysis

The area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (AUC) in the random order was compared with those in the density and SSL orders. ROC curves were plotted, and their AUC values and 95% confidence intervals were calculated using the radiologists' probability of malignancy scores (ranging from 0 to 100) in a multireader multicase analysis of variance, using the iMRMC software package (version 4.0.3, Division of Imaging, Diagnostics, and Software Reliability, Office of Science and Engineering Laboratories, Center for Devices and Radiological Health, U.S. Food and Drug Administration). In the analysis of variance model, three factors were included: modality (reading order), reader, and case (screening examination); these three factors are considered standard effects in multireader multicase studies (40–42). Modality was a fixed effect, as the three reading orders selected were included in this study. Readers and cases were treated as cross-correlated random effects because of the interest in generalizing to the population of readers and cases for the specific comparisons that were indicated (42–44). The software estimated all components of variance (variances and covariances) using a “one-shot” nonparametric estimate based on the properties of U statistics, providing unbiased estimates of variance components, accounting for variability and correlations between readers and cases.

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Appendix S5– Additional tables and figures

Table S1: Area Under the Curve of the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curves for each of the Radiologists Reading Screening Mammography Examinations That Were Ordered Randomly, by Increasing Volumetric Breast Density, or by Self-supervised Learning (SSL).

Reader	Random	Density	SSL
R1	0.94	0.92	0.95
R2	0.92	0.93	0.89
R3	0.87	0.92	0.91
R4	0.92	0.94	0.91
R5	0.94	0.95	0.95
R6	0.92	0.93	0.92
R7	0.93	0.95	0.85
R8	0.91	0.92	0.93
R9	0.92	0.95	0.93
R10	0.94	0.96	0.91
R11	0.92	0.94	0.89
R12	0.89	0.90	0.95
R13	0.94	0.95	0.94
Average	0.92 (0.89, 0.95)	0.93 (0.91, 0.96)	0.92 (0.89, 0.95)
<i>P</i> value		.009	.70

Note. - 95% CIs are shown within parentheses.

Table S2: Specificity & Sensitivity for Each of the Radiologists Reading Screening Mammography Examinations That Were Ordered Randomly, by Increasing Volumetric Breast Density, or by Self-supervised Learning (SSL).

Reader	Random	Density	SSL
Specificity			
R1	87 (65/75)	81 (61/75)	77 (58/75)
R2	93 (70/75)	91 (68/75)	88 (66/75)
R3	84 (63/75)	84 (63/75)	88 (66/75)
R4	85 (64/75)	91 (68/75)	88 (66/75)
R5	83 (62/75)	99 (74/75)	91 (68/75)
R6	87 (65/75)	88 (66/75)	81 (61/75)
R7	93 (70/75)	93 (70/75)	79 (59/75)
R8	72 (54/75)	76 (57/75)	71 (53/75)
R9	87 (65/75)	88 (66/75)	85 (64/75)
R10	81 (61/75)	91 (68/75)	87 (65/75)
R11	87 (65/75)	92 (69/75)	81 (61/75)
R12	91 (68/75)	99 (74/75)	97 (73/75)
R13	87 (65/75)	89 (67/75)	80 (60/75)
Average	86 (81, 91)	89 (84, 94)	84 (78, 90)
<i>P</i> value		.04	.37
Sensitivity			
R1	87 (65/75)	91 (68/75)	89 (67/75)
R2	65 (49/75)	83 (62/75)	76 (57/75)
R3	76 (57/75)	81 (61/75)	73 (55/75)
R4	80 (60/75)	76 (57/75)	81 (61/75)
R5	87 (65/75)	76 (57/75)	84 (63/75)
R6	85 (64/75)	84 (63/75)	83 (62/75)
R7	79 (59/75)	79 (59/75)	80 (60/75)
R8	89 (67/75)	88 (66/75)	88 (66/75)
R9	79 (59/75)	89 (67/75)	84 (63/75)
R10	85 (64/75)	85 (64/75)	76 (57/75)
R11	83 (62/75)	76 (57/75)	81 (61/75)
R12	69 (52/75)	65 (49/75)	63 (47/75)
R13	87 (65/75)	85 (64/75)	87 (65/75)
Average	81 (74, 88)	81 (74, 88)	80 (74, 87)
<i>P</i> value		.78	.79

Note. - Specificity & sensitivity are shown in percentages with the numerator and denominator shown in parentheses. For average values, 95% CIs are shown in parentheses

Table S3: Radiologist-averaged Sensitivities across Various histopathologic Tumor Types, Tumor Sizes, and Lesion Types When Reading Screening Mammography Examinations That Were Ordered Randomly, by Increasing Volumetric Breast Density, or by Self-supervised Learning (SSL).

Subanalyses	Random	Density	SSL
Histopathologic tumor type			
Invasive NST	87 (521/598)	86 (515/598)	87 (523/598)
DCIS	68 (141/208)	71 (147/208)	65 (135/208)
ILC	86 (78/91)	87 (79/91)	79 (72/91)
Mixed NST/ILC	74 (48/65)	82 (53/65)	82 (53/65)
Other invasive	0 (0/13)	0 (0/13)	8 (1/13)
Tumor size			
0-10 mm	88 (161/182)	87 (159/182)	87 (158/182)
10-20 mm	88 (276/312)	89 (276/312)	89 (277/312)
20-50 mm	75 (166/221)	76 (169/221)	76 (169/221)
≥50 mm	73 (19/26)	85 (22/26)	69 (18/26)
Missing	71 (166/234)	72 (168/234)	69 (162/234)
Lesion type			
Mass	80 (438/546)	80 (439/546)	81 (444/546)
Calcifications	79 (217/273)	83 (227/273)	78 (212/273)
Mass + calcifications	95 (74/78)	91 (71/78)	95 (74/78)
Architectural distortion	100 (13/13)	85 (11/13)	85 (11/13)
Architectural distortion + calcifications	81 (21/26)	69 (18/26)	69 (18/26)
Asymmetric density	64 (25/39)	72 (28/39)	64 (25/39)

Note. - Data are radiologist-averaged sensitivity percentages with the numerator and denominator shown in parentheses. DCIS = ductal carcinoma in situ, ILC = invasive lobular carcinoma, NST = no special type.

Table S4: Median Outcomes Per Examination for each of the Radiologists Reading Screening Mammography Examinations That Were Ordered Randomly, by Increasing Volumetric Breast Density, or by Self-supervised Learning (SSL).

Reader	Random	Density	SSL
Reading time			
R1	27.7	18.4	19.3
R2	36.1	29.7	34.9
R3	18.4	16.0	14.8
R4	34.8	35.4	35.8
R5	36.2	41.9	35.5
R6	15.9	15.2	17.5
R7	22.3	21.9	27.4
R8	24.7	25.5	24.6
R9	28.6	34.8	39.8
R10	26.0	16.6	23.9
R11	26.1	28.1	31.9
R12	36.6	24.7	28.3
R13	27.5	26.0	33.3
Average	27.8	25.7	28.2
Number of fixations			
R1	54	33	35
R2	82	75	74
R3	30	23	20
R4	47	72	57
R5	73	75	65
R6	27	25	28
R7	35	34	47
R8	50	46	47
R9	62	75	86
R10	47	25	39
R11	46	56	74
R12	87	55	63
R13	54	46	68
Average	53	49	54
Fixation time in lesion region			
R1	5.0	2.9	3.1
R2	6.7	5.9	6.9
R3	3.6	3.0	3.0
R4	3.4	5.3	5.7
R5	7.2	6.2	8.2
R6	2.9	2.3	2.4
R7	4.7	4.0	4.7
R8	3.3	3.3	4.1
R9	5.8	5.8	7.1
R10	3.4	2.4	3.0
R11	3.9	3.7	4.9
R12	4.9	3.0	3.6
R13	4.7	4.7	6.1

Average	4.6	4.0	4.8
TTF in lesion region			
R1	0.8	0.8	0.7
R2	1.0	0.8	0.8
R3	0.8	0.9	0.9
R4	1.5	1.1	1.0
R5	1.3	1.1	1.3
R6	0.7	0.9	1.1
R7	0.7	0.8	0.7
R8	1.3	1.1	0.9
R9	2.8	2.7	2.5
R10	1.1	1.0	1.0
R11	1.7	1.6	1.0
R12	4.8	5.8	6.4
R13	0.9	1.0	0.8
Average	1.5	1.5	1.5

Note. - Reading times, time in the lesion region, and time to first fixation (TTF) in the lesion region are shown in seconds.

Figure S1: Illustration of the reader study interface. The radiologists were asked three questions: “Give your suspicion of malignancy” (ranging from normal to unsure to radiologically malignant), “What density do these images have?,” and “Would you recall this woman?” (with possible answers: no and yes). The questions were originally presented in Dutch.

Figure S2: Plots indicating the frequency of consecutive cancer and noncancer examinations for the three different reading orders. SSL, self-supervised learning.

Figure S3: Reader-averaged receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves for the radiologists reading screening mammography examinations that were ordered by increasing volumetric breast density (blue), randomly (red), and by self-supervised learning (SSL) (green). The dots indicate radiologists' operating points based on their recall decisions. The area under the ROC curves are shown together with 95% CIs. It should be noted, however, that the CIs are considerably wider than the differences between the ROC curves. The errors characterized by the bands are representative of each curve individually, but they are not representative of the differences between the curves. The differences between the ROC curves are smaller because of correlations due to common readers and cases (in the same way that a paired comparison may be able to detect a small difference between two variables with large variances). Our hypotheses are not focused on the individual ROC curves (or the absolute value of the area under the ROC), but rather on the differences between them. And thus, these CIs are not directly relevant to our hypotheses. AUC = area under the ROC curve, FPR = false-positive rate, TPR = true-positive rate.

Figure S4: Violin plots show median reading times of the radiologists reading screening mammography examinations that were ordered randomly (red), by increasing volumetric breast density (blue), and by self-supervised learning (SSL) (green), categorized by Volpara Density Grades (categories a, b, c, and d). The Volpara Density Grades correlate with visual BI-RADS 5th edition density categories (a < 3.5%, 3.5% ≤ b < 7.5%, 7.5% ≤ c < 15.5%, d ≥ 15.5%). The random reading order was compared against the density and SSL order, and the asterisks indicate statistical significance: *** $P < .000125$, ** $P < .00125$, * $P < .00625$.

Figure S5: Violin plots show median reading times of the radiologists reading screening mammography examinations that were ordered randomly (red), by increasing volumetric breast density (blue), and by self-supervised learning (SSL) (green), categorized by consensus and nonconsensus cancer and noncancers examinations. For the consensus examinations all radiologists agreed on the recall decision for all three orders. For the nonconsensus examinations some radiologists had different recall decisions in some orders. The random reading order was compared against the density and SSL order, and the asterisks indicate statistical significance: *** $P < .000125$, ** $P < .00125$, * $P < .00625$.

Figure S6: Violin plots show total number of fixations (including fixations in both craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique views) for the radiologists reading screening mammography examinations that were ordered randomly (red), by increasing volumetric breast density (blue), and by self-supervised learning (SSL) (green), categorized by consensus and nonconsensus cancer and noncancers examinations. For the consensus examinations all radiologists agreed on the recall decision for all three orders. For the nonconsensus examinations some radiologists had different recall decisions in some orders. The random reading order was compared against the density and SSL order, and the asterisks indicate statistical significance: *** $P < .000125$.

Figure S7: Violin plots show fixation time in the 20 mm radius malignant lesion regions for the radiologists reading screening mammography examinations that were ordered randomly (red), by increasing volumetric breast density (blue), and by self-supervised learning (SSL) (green), categorized by consensus and nonconsensus cancer and noncancers examinations. For the consensus examinations all radiologists agreed on the recall decision for all three orders. For the nonconsensus examinations some radiologists had different recall decisions in some orders. The random reading order was compared against the density and SSL order, and the asterisks indicate statistical significance: **** $P < .00025$, ** $P < .0025$.

Figure S8: Violin plots show time to first fixation (TTF) at the 20 mm radius malignant lesion region for the radiologists reading screening mammography examinations that were ordered randomly (red), by increasing volumetric breast density (blue), and by self-supervised learning (SSL) (green), categorized by consensus and nonconsensus cancer and noncancers examinations. For the consensus examinations all radiologists agreed on the recall decision for all three orders. For the nonconsensus examinations some radiologists had different recall decisions in some orders. The random reading order was compared against the density and SSL order.

Figure S9: Change in radiologists' perceived Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System density categories a-d. (A) Density- versus random-ordered readings. (B) Self-supervised learning- (SSL) versus random-ordered readings. The figure aggregates the comparisons of all radiologist-examination pairs.